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Remediation experiment of Ecuadorian acid mine drainage: geochemical models of dissolved species and secondary minerals saturation.

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Abstract:	<p>Acid mine drainage is one of the main environmental hazards to ecosystems worldwide and it is directly related to mining activities. In Ecuador, such acidic-metallic waters are drained to rivers without treatment. In this research, we tested a laboratory combined (Ca-Mg) Dispersed Alkaline Substrate (DAS) system as an alternative to remediate acid drainage from the Zaruma-Portovelo gold mining site, at El Oro, Ecuador. The system worked at low and high flow hydraulic rates during a period of 8 months, without signs of saturation. . Analysis of physico-chemical parameters and water composition (ICP-OES, ICP-MS) demonstrated that treatment effectively increased water pH and promoted the retention of about 80% of Fe, Al, Mn and Cu. Under acid conditions As, Cr and Pb concentrations decreased with Fe and possible precipitation of jarosite and schwertmannite. However, the homogeneous depletion of Cr at pH above 6 could be related to ferrihydrite or directly with Cr(OH)₃ precipitation. After DAS-Ca, sulphate, phosphate and rare earth elements (REE) concentrations decreased to 1912, 0.85 and 0.07 mg/L respectively, while DAS-Mg contributed to form a complex model of minor carbonate and phosphate phases as main sink of REE. DAS-Mg also promoted the retention of most divalent metals at pH values over seven. Thus, this low cost treatment could avoid environmental pollution and international conflicts. Anyway, further investigations are needed to obtain higher Zn retention values.</p>	
Response to Reviewers:	Dear Editor, Hereby we send the second response to reviewers.	

	<p>We sincerely acknowledge the three referees the work made on improving our investigation and hope we can meet again and share experiences on our field.</p> <p>Dear reviewer#3, the authors apologize for this omission which was absolutely not intentionally. We are totally agree with the reviewer on supressing this statement because it was a subjective observation but not a scientific result.</p> <p>Dear reviewer#5, Certainly, many mistakes in spaces have been corrected. Moreover, we have unified the expression mg/L, because sometimes appeared as mg·L-1 (which has been supressed)</p> <p>Also, figures have been sent to the journal in .tiff format of checked quality.</p>
Additional Information:	
Question	Response
§Are you submitting to a Special Issue?	No

Dear Editor,

Hereby we send the second response to reviewers.

We sincerely acknowledge the three referees the work made on improving our investigation and hope we can meet again and share experiences on our field.

Reviewer #1:

Revised version is OK

Reviewer #3:

The statements made by authors at page 14, line 257/258 are not supported by their experimental data (" A visual observation of the precipitated layers in the first centimetres of the column DAS-Ca shows the important role of Fe(III) controlling trace element retention ("ochre layer", Fig. 2a, 2a)"). The authors neither made an analytical study of Iron speciation (or phase determination in solid material), nor made a extraction/fractionation of trace elements in sediments. So this statement need to be remove/changed. This is the second time that I ask for this change. From my point of view if the author´s refuse in made this modification the manuscript can not be published.

Dear reviewer, the authors apologize for this omission which was absolutely not intentionally. We are totally agree with the reviewer on supress this statement because it was a subjective observation but not a scientific result.

Reviewer #5:

The responses to Reviewers' comments provided by the authors of manuscript ESPR-D-19-03119R1 are satisfactory. However, metric units (Lines 48, 130, 131 and in other parts of manuscript) must be separated from digits presented. Improved quality graphics should be provided for better resolution.

Certainly, many mistakes in spaces have been corrected. Moreover, we have unified the expression mg/L, because sometimes appeared as mg·L⁻¹ (which has been supressed) Also, figures have been sent to the journal in .tiff format of checked quality.

34 1. Introduction

1 35 Acid mine drainage (AMD) generated from abandoned mining activities and uncontrolled tailing dumps is
2
3 36 a global socio-environmental concern. Acidic waters are produced from the oxidation of pyrite and other
4
5 37 metal sulphides disposed as million tons of sulphate-rich wastes worldwide. Such wastes once exposed to
6
7 38 oxidation under atmospheric conditions generate highly acid leachates with extreme concentrations of
8
9 39 metal-metalloids and sulphates known as AMD (Ayala et al., 2015; Younger et al., 2002). Extended areas
10
11 40 of streams directly affected by AMD present poor water quality incapable of sustaining a healthy macro-
12
13 41 life (e.g., fish) (Bigham and Cravotta, 2016).

14
15
16 42 AMD mainly affects the quality of waters draining mining sites. In Ecuador, for example, mining sites
17
18 43 located in the southern part have affected the Puyango River basin, one of the most important basins that
19
20 44 flows to the Pacific Ocean crossing southern Ecuador and northern Peru (Betancourt et al., 2005). In its
21
22 45 upper course, the Puyango River flows through the Zaruma-Portovelo gold mining site (Fig. 1). The climate
23
24 46 of the area is characterised by a high variability of temperature and precipitation with a mega-thermal dry
25
26 47 weather dominating Portovelo (mean annual temperatures of 24 °C and precipitation oscillating between
27
28 48 500 and 2000 mm). Zaruma-Portovelo is located over the palaeozoic metamorphic complex of El Oro,
29
30 49 covered by cretaceous volcanic rocks and subsequently intruded by cenozoic igneous complexes. The ore
31
32 50 at this site consist mainly of gold and silver, included in quartz veins associated to sulfides aspyrite,
33
34 51 chalcopyrite, galena, sphalerite (PRODEMINCA, 1999). Metallurgical processing plants implies a variety
35
36 52 of methods for precious metal recovery from ore extracted within and outside the Zaruma-Portovelo district.
37
38 53 Such variability of ore sources and ore processing methods have led to the release of Fe, Cu, Pb, Zn, As,
39
40 54 Cd, and Bi from geochemically heterogeneous tailings, harder to dispose and difficult to monitor (Delgado
41
42 55 et al., 2018). Around 87 to 110 small-scale active processing plants (Fig. 1) in the Zaruma-Portovelo mining
43
44 56 site (Pazmiño, 2013) store tailings in dams located at the river edges or release them directly to the river. A
45
46 57 potential product from the oxidation of such tailings is AMD. Recent studies demonstrated how mining
47
48 58 activities impacted negatively on Amarillo River and the Calera River, effluents of the Puyango watershed
49
50 59 (Tarras-Wahlberg et al. 2001; Tarras-Wahlerberg and Lane, 2003; Guimarães et al., 2011; Ayala and López,
51
52 60 2014).

53
54
55
56 61 In 2008, considering the Binational Convention Puyango-Tumbes (1971), the Republic of Peru promoted
57
58 62 an international claim against Ecuador, due to the extreme pollution detected in the lower part of Puyango
59
60 63 watershed. Since then, Ecuadorian government has promoted continuous efforts to address this situation.

64 However, wider knowledge on the toxic elements cycles and development of novel techniques for
65 environmental remediation are necessary to implement a correct basin management.

66 In this sense, several remediation strategies have been designed to reduce the environmental impact of mine
67 tailings around the world. One option is the application of active treatments consisting of controlled addition
68 of chemicals into the acidic discharge and/or wastes to increase pH and decrease metals mobility. However,
69 active treatments are expensive (Skousen et al., 1990), impracticable at abandoned sites, and generate
70 products even harder to dispose. On the other hand, passive treatment systems (PTS) do not need continuous
71 addition of reagents and require occasional maintenance, becoming an economic option for AMD
72 remediation. Typical AMD treatment systems tends to lose reactivity or permeability due to the formation
73 of precipitates coating the limestone grains or filling the pore space of the system (Simon et al., 2005; Pérez-
74 López et al. 2007). To address these problems, Rötting, Thomas, Ayora and Carrera (2008) developed the
75 Dispersed Alkaline Substrate (DAS), which consists of a reactive mixture of wood shavings and limestone
76 sand. The high metal removal performance of this reactive mixture has been tested both in laboratory
77 columns (Rötting, Thomas et al., 2008) and field-scale experiments (Rötting, Caraballo, Serrano, Ayora
78 and Carrera, 2008; Caraballo, Rötting, Nieto and Ayora, 2009). Nevertheless, DAS could be insufficient to
79 remediate high concentrations of divalent metals such as Zn, Mn, Ni or Cd (Rötting, Ayora and Carrera,
80 2008) since: (i) under field conditions, calcite dissolution only raises pH values around 7, insufficient to
81 precipitate divalent metals (Cortina et al., 2003). (ii) At extremely high concentrations, metals could be
82 toxic to sulphate reducing bacteria, responsible for inducing precipitation of metal-sulphides (Cabrera et
83 al., 2006). (iii) Sorption and exchange sites may be rapidly saturated under high metal loads (Gibert et al.,
84 2005).

85 Rötting et al. (2006) conducted laboratory column experiments that demonstrated that caustic magnesia
86 (MgO) could be used to remove high concentrations of divalent metals from solution. Reactivity of MgO
87 was improved when mixed with quartz sand or wood fragments, which favoured the creation of a more
88 reactive and permeable substrate. In fact, a combined DAS (Ca-Mg) created a more reactive substrate
89 system with a higher-porosity matrix and a large surface area that accelerated reaction kinetics and
90 enhanced its permeability, two great advantages for a passive AMD treatment system such as DAS.

91 This technology has been successfully applied at sites with moderate-high acidity and metal concentrations
92 under humid climate (i.e. Rötting et al., 2006; Rötting, Ayora and Carrera, 2008; Rötting, Caraballo, et al.
93 2008; Rötting, Thomas et al., 2008; Caraballo, Rötting, Macías, Nieto and Ayora 2009; Caraballo, Rötting,

94 Nieto et al. 2009, Caraballo et al. 2011; Macías et al., 2012). However, the effectiveness of the passive
95 treatment (DAS-type) has not been tested in dry-megathermic climate conditions or AMD generated from
96 tailings generated in the Zaruma-Portovelo mining district.

97 On the other hand, Rare Earth Elements (REE) have been frequently used as environmental tracers because
98 they help us to estimate the affection degree of polluted sites by mining activities (i.e., Olías et al., 2005;
99 López-González et al., 2012; Delgado et al., 2012). In addition, REE (especially Eu, Tm, Lu and Y) are
100 now widely used in several technologies, from clean energy tomilitary systems (Zhou et al., 2016). This
101 trend will lead to a continuous increase in demand for REE in the coming decades (Alonso et al., 2012),
102 which will be traduced in a higher request for global production of REE. Normally, REE are associated
103 with Ca, Th and U, so their appearance is not consistent with the demand for individual elements. This
104 poses restrictions on the survey of REE projects (Zhou et al., 2017). For this reason, recent studies are
105 lending special interest in their behaviour under acidic environments condition (e.g. Ayora et al., 2016;
106 Macias et al., 2017) and focusing their effort to determine the degree of REE recuperation from AMD
107 treatment systems, providing added value to the process by reusing the waste. REE concentration in waters
108 decreases as pH increase, which is usually the result of simultaneous processes as sorption to suspended
109 particles (Gammons et al., 2005), coprecipitation with Al- and Fe- oxyhydroxides and the complexation
110 with humic substances flocculants (Åström et al., 2012). This pH dependence has been observed by
111 analyzing AMD neutralization processes at both laboratory (Verplanck et al., 2004) and basin scales
112 (Delgado et al., 2012), concluding that there exists a preferential HREE (heavy rare earth) partition over
113 LREE (light) in the solid phase as pH increases above 6. Nevertheless, few studies aboard REE fractionation
114 at alkaline conditions, suggesting that carbonates (Ayora et al., 2016) and phosphates (Delgado et al., 2012)
115 exert a certain control in the processes of fractionation of REE at the end of the series.

116 Therefore, the aims of the present study were: 1) to test the effectiveness of a combined DAS (Ca-Mg)
117 reactive substrate system to decontaminate AMD, by monitoring hydrogeochemical and thermo-hydraulic
118 conditions at laboratory scale. 2) To set design guidelines for a future pilot-field scale implementation,
119 based on the laboratory efficiency results under the existing climate conditions (dry-megathermic climate).
120 3) To gain a better understanding of REE cycles in environmental systems affected by AMD production
121 through the study of the fractionation between aqueous and solid phases, that could be used in future studies
122 of waste reusing.

123

124 2. Materials and methods

125 2.1. Experimental design – Laboratory Columns

126 A combined DAS (Ca-Mg) reactive substrate system to treat AMD (Rötting, Ayora and Carrera, 2008;
127 Rötting, Thomas et al., 2008) was implemented at the National Research Institute of Geology, Mining and
128 Metallurgy (INIGEMM) laboratories in Quito-Ecuador, as shown in Fig. 2a, 2a'. The matrix of the DAS-
129 Ca column was composed of 25% (v/v) of 94% purity CaCO₃ sand (0.1–2 mm grain size) and 75% (v/v)
130 wood chips (thickness up to 1 mm, 0.5 mm mean grain size). The matrix of the Das-Mg column was a
131 mixture of 12.5% (v/v) commercial reactive magnesium oxide (MgO) dust (0.15 mm median particle size)
132 and 87.5% (v/v) wood chips. The column bottoms were filled with local quartz gravels (3–5 mm diameter).
133 AMD collected from two sources (section 2.2) was stored under laboratory conditions in plastic containers
134 to create a *Natural Fe-Oxidizing Lagoon (NFOL)* where part of the Fe(II) is biotically and abiotically
135 oxidized and hence removed from solution (Macías et al., 2012). A peristaltic pump (LongerPump®
136 BT100-1 L) pumped the partially treated effluent to the DAS-Ca column, from which it flowed to the DAS-
137 Mg column. The experience was conducted in duplicate (Fig. 2a).

138 To start the experiment, both columns were slowly saturated with AMD and a permanent level of solution
139 was maintained as a supernatant (see Fig. 2b). The system performed a low flow rate period (7 months) and
140 a high flow rate period (4 weeks) to test the efficiency of the columns with different hydraulic residence
141 times. Assuming a mean porosity of 50%, (Rotting, Ayora and Carrera, 2008) and Darcy constant velocities
142 of 0.8 ml/min and 1.4 ml/min, the mean flow rates were 0.096 m³/m²d (0.66 L/day, with 8 days residence
143 time) and 0.21 m³/m²d (1.44 L/day, assuming 3 days residence time) for low and high flow rate,
144 respectively.

145

146 2.2. Field water analysis and monitoring

147 Two AMD-sources located in the Zaruma-Portovelo mining site (ZPMS) were selected for water samples
148 collection (Fig. 1). The first point, *AMD-Buza* consisted on a leachate derived from environmental
149 liabilities (located near the confluence of Amarillo and Calera rivers). The strong seasonality (hot-dry
150 climate conditions) and lack of rain over a long period produced the drying of this creek. Therefore, the
151 AMD sampling site changed to the nearby *AMD-Torata* mine shaft, characterized by a permanent flow.

152 This change allowed us simulating the response of the combined DAS (Ca-Mg) reactive to variable
153 hydrochemical characteristics of input acid leachates derived from geochemically heterogeneous tailings
154 (Delgado et al., 2018).

155 During the experiment, the system was working at open laboratory conditions (environmental variation of
156 temperature). Climatic data were obtained from INANHI (National Institute of Meteorology and
157 Hydrology) for inter-annual treatment period. Water samples along the columns were collected from the
158 sampling ports showed in Fig. 2b. The inflow container (AMD-Input; #1), supernatant water (Supra-; #2
159 and #7), drain pipe (Out-#6 and #11), and Output container (Out-Final; #12) were sampling every 15 days.
160 Samples from the intermediate sampling ports located in the reactive zones (#3, 4, 5, 8, 9 and 10) were
161 taken monthly.

162 Physico-chemical parameters pH, electrical conductivity (E.C.), redox potential (Eh), dissolved oxygen
163 (D.O.) and temperature (T) were measured using a multi-parameter sensor (HANNA HI9828). Major
164 cations and trace elements were measured in filtered water samples (0.2 μm) by inductively coupled
165 plasma-atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES, model Optima 8300, Perkin Elmer, detection limits in
166 Table 1). REE were determined by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectroscopy (ICP-MS, model
167 Agilent 7500ce). Dissolved sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) and phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) were determined by UV-Vis
168 spectrometry using a HACH DR6000 spectrophotometer with 10 mL quartz cells. Sulphate analysis was
169 based on a turbidimetric method 4500- SO_4^{2-} E methodology with barium chloride (APHA, 2012a).
170 Phosphate was quantified following the APHA method 4500-PE and adapted with a standard addition
171 technique to eliminate the arsenate interference (APHA, 2012b).

172 Certified ICP Multi-Element standard solutions from AccuStandard, SQS-01-1CRM and SQS-02-R1-
173 1CRM according to the EPA 200.7 and EPA 6010 Series, were used for calibration and accuracy control.
174 Additionally, certified reference material for Effluents/Inorganic/Metal (n°1244) and inter-laboratory test
175 for Trace Metals (Water Pollution/Trace Metals n°586) (CRM-European environmental production) are
176 also measured as internal periodic laboratory control. Beside, nine replicates (one for each sampled matrix)
177 were analysed to check the quality of the analysis whose relative percentage difference (% RPD) revealed
178 low mean values for Al, Fe, Mn, SO_4^{2-} (<5%) and for Mg, Co, Ni, Pb, Zn, Cu (<10%) and acceptable values
179 for As, Cd, Cr (<18%). Total alkalinity was measured using CHEMetrics "Titrets" test kits (range 10-100
180 or 100-1000 mg/L as CaCO_3 , with 5% accuracy). Hydraulic conductivity K (cm/s) was calculated using
181 Darcy's Law to track the reactivity of the system (Equation 1), where Q (ml/s) is flow rate, A (cm^2) is the

182 tank cross-section area perpendicular to flow, and L and Δh (cm) are distances and head-loss between
183 control surfaces, respectively.

$$184 \quad K = QL / A \Delta h \quad [1]$$

185 Net acidity (mg/L as CaCO₃ equivalents) was calculated according to Kirby and Cravotta (2005) (Equation
186 2), where C_X are molar concentrations (mol/L) and alk is measured as total alkalinity (mg/L as CaCO₃
187 equivalents).

$$188 \quad \text{Net acidity} = 50,045 \times (3c_{Al} + 2c_{Fe} + 2c_{Mn} + 2c_{Zn} + 10^{-pH}) - \text{alk} \quad [2]$$

189 Absolute net acidity elimination and relative metal removal (r), where C_{sup} is AMD-Input concentration
190 (mg/L) and C_{out} is Out-Final concentration (mg/L), were also calculated (Equation 3 and 4, respectively).

$$191 \quad \text{Net acidity elimination} = \text{Supernatant net acidity} - \text{Drain pipe net acidity} \quad [3]$$

$$192 \quad r = (C_{sup} - C_{out} / C_{sup}) \times 100 \quad [4]$$

194 *2.3. Geochemical Modelling of major ions, trace elements and rare earth elements.*

195 Activity and chemical speciation of dissolved species (AS, aqueous species) and the saturation indexes (SI,
196 Equation 5) of minerals in solution present in the two columns (DAS-Ca and DAS-Mg) of the system at
197 the end of the treatment (Torata last sampling, 20/02/2015), were calculated using *PHREEQC* modelling
198 (version 3.1.7; Parkhurst and Appelo, 1999). The thermodynamic database of *PHREEQC* was enlarged
199 with data from geochemical code *WATEQ4F* (Ball and Nordstrom, 1991). Solubility constants (KS) for
200 schwertmannite were extracted from literature (Bigham et al., 1996) and SI were obtained following the
201 detailed methodology described in Delgado et al., (2009).

$$202 \quad SI = \log (IAP / KS) \quad [5]$$

203 Where SI the saturation index, IAP the ion activity product, and KS the solubility constant.

204 REE concentrations were normalized to the upper crust using the North-American Shale Composite
205 (NASC) values. Finally, partition processes of the main lanthanides aqueous species from the AMD Out-
206 Final solution were established using *CHEAQS-Next* modelling (Verweij, 2007) with stability constants of
207 the REE sulphates complexes from NIST compilation (Martell et al., 2004).

208 **2.4. Middle REE enrichment.**

1 209 The enrichment/depletion in middle REE (MREE) gives upward concave (V-type) and convex (Λ -type)
2
3 210 quantifiable patterns according to the traditional NASC-normalized $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ ratio. However, using a
4
5 211 single rare earth as representative of a set could hamper the interpretation of REE patterns in the case of
6
7 212 exclusive fractionation affecting only that rare earth. Therefore, it would be crucial to assess the significance
8
9 213 of the curvature effect in the MREE whole segment (Pérez-López et al., 2010). For this reason, we have
10
11 214 calculated the index E_{MREE} (Enrichment of middle REE) to quantify this effect as the normalized maximum
12
13 215 vertical difference between the polynomial curve fitting of the MREE region and its theoretical Y-axis
14
15 216 position in the absence of enrichment or depletion (see details of the calculation method in Pérez-López et
16
17 217 al. (2010) and Delgado et al. (2012). $E_{MREE} < 0$ and $E_{MREE} > 0$ represent depletion (concave pattern) and
18
19 218 enrichment (convex pattern) in MREE, respectively, and thus around zero the flat patterns. The quality of
20
21 219 the fit, and hence the significance of the curve formed by data points, was quantified by the squared
22
23 220 correlation coefficient, R^2 .

24
25
26
27 221

28 29 222 **3. Results and Discussion**

30 31 223 **3.1. Hydrochemical evaluation of the combined DAS system to treat Ecuadorian mine waters.**

32
33 224 The combined DAS (Ca-Mg) reactive substrate system was constantly monitored (Table 1). The control
34
35 225 points appear numbered in Fig.2b. The pH of AMD-Input (#1) and Supra-Ca (#2) solutions had mean values
36
37 226 from 2.7 to 2.4 and 4.1 to 2.3, respectively and values of E.C. characteristic of high-mineralized waters,
38
39 227 subjected to moderate or high Ecuadorian restrictions for use in crops (MAE, 2000). After the DAS-Ca, an
40
41 228 increase in water pH (up to 6.2), alkalinity (up to 263 mg/L) and Ca concentrations (up to 1128 mg/L), as
42
43 229 well as a decrease in acidity, took place due to limestone dissolution (Fig. 3a, b). This process induced the
44
45 230 removal of Fe and Al (Fig. 3c, d) and the adsorption-coprecipitation of As, Cr and Pb even at low
46
47 231 concentrations (Fig. 3e, f).

48
49
50
51 232 The decrease in concentration of Al and sulphates (Fig. 3a, b) during the early stages of the treatment, led
52
53 233 to a subsequent protons removal, pH increase and could be related with Cu removal (Fig.3c) by
54
55 234 coprecipitation processes (Hammarstrom et al., 2005). On the other hand, the circum-neutral conditions
56
57 235 observed in the DAS-Ca was not enough for divalent metal hydroxides to form (Cortina et al., 2003). At
58
59 236 the supernatant of DAS-Mg (Supra-Mg #7) pH increased up to 6.7, related with the dissolution of reactive

237 magnesia (Mg concentrations changes from 212 to 699 mg/L) and also with the long retention time which
238 improved retention of Fe and Al as acidity decreased. Water samples at the contact with MgO presented Al
239 contents below 0.16 mg/L and Fe contents below 0.13 mg/L (Table 1). This almost absence of trivalent
240 elements has been exposed as the best scenario to guarantee an optimal performance of the MgO in the
241 subsequent steps of the treatment (Caraballo, Rötting, Macías et al., 2009). After the percolation through
242 the Mg column, Cd, Co and Ni concentrations decreased down to 0.01 mg/L, Mn decreased down to 1.71
243 mg/L, and Zn decreased down to 1.05 mg/L, which was directly related to the increase of Mg concentration
244 and pH (Fig. 3a, b). According to Baes and Mesmer (1976), the more effective retention of divalent metals
245 by hydroxides should be achieved when pH is between 8 and 10. Finally, the preservation of the waters in
246 an Output container enabled their stability by equilibrium with atmospheric CO₂, reducing even more the
247 trace element concentrations and pH (Table 1, Out-Final #12).

248 The combined DAS (Ca-Mg) reactive substrate system performed effectively. The acidity of the tested
249 AMD waters was suppressed (Fig. 4a), even achieving negatives values (indicative of net alkaline waters).
250 Similar results were also obtained by Rötting, Thomas et al. (2008) and Macias et al. (2012) for equivalent
251 treatments. Similar patterns were depicted by Al (Fig. 4b), total Fe (Fig. 4c) and Zn (Fig. 4d), which across
252 the columns and along time were progressively removed from solution without signs of reactive saturation.

253

254 **3.2. Hydrogeochemical Modelling**

255 **3.2.1. Aqueous solution species and solid-phases saturation index**

256 **3.2.1.1. Iron speciation**

257 Iron was depleted from solution in the DAS-Ca column (Table 2, Fig. 5a) probably as low-crystalline
258 oxyhydroxydes or oxy-hydroxysulfates. According to the hydrochemical model, the soluble Fe species
259 before Mid2-Ca (#4) were FeSO₄⁺ (73%) and Fe(SO₄)₂⁻ (14%). Minor proportion of Fe(III), Fe(II), FeOH⁺²,
260 Fe(OH)₂⁺ and FeHPO₄⁺ (3%) appeared at the contact with the Ca-column (#2 or Supra-Ca). Di-sulphate
261 species, representative in AMD, at high SO₄²⁻ concentration (> 150 mg/L), were removed from solution,
262 increasing the proportion of hydrolysed species (Shum and Lavkullich, 1998). In such conditions,
263 precipitation of saturated Fe phases, H-jarosite [(H₃O)Fe₃(SO₄)₂(OH)₆], K-jarosite [KFe₃(SO₄)₂(OH)₆],
264 schwertmannite [Fe₈O₈(OH)₆(SO₄)], ferrihydrite [Fe(OH)₃], hematite [α-Fe₂O₃], goethite [α-FeOOH],

265 lepidocrocite [γ -FeOOH] and maghemite [γ -Fe₂O₃], could have occurred along the DAS-Ca column (Fig.
266 5a).

267 As can be seen in Fig. 2a', the progressive increase of pH favors the formation of an "ochre" horizon in
268 the first centimeters, followed of a "white" horizon, which probably correspond to Fe and Al precipitates,
269 respectively, also described by Rötting et al. (2008). In this sense, according the data model H-jarosite and
270 K-jarosite were saturated at acidic pH values (before Mid1-Ca #3, mean values SI =5.60 and 6.66,
271 respectively), so are likely to be present, although the distinction between both phases is difficult (Sánchez-
272 España et al., 2016). Only Mid2-Ca #4 solutions (pH = 5.8) were supersaturated in schwertmannite (Fig.
273 5b, SI = 7.37), the most common mineral associated to ochre precipitates at slightly acidic pH, whose
274 saturation is controlled by [Fe³⁺] activity (Yu et al., 1999). When solution became neutral (Mid2-Ca #4,
275 pH>6), ferrihydrite probably started playing a role in metal retention. Likewise, hematite, goethite,
276 lepidocrocite and maghemite showed positive saturation index at practically all control points (Fig. 5a).
277 However, goethite and hematite do not usually appear as direct precipitates from AMD, due to their
278 precipitation kinetics, but they are formed by transformation of Fe oxyhydroxide-sulphates (Acero et al.,
279 2006; Marescotti et al., 2012). Similarly, maghemite can also be formed through dehydration and
280 transformation of lepidocrocite and ferrihydrite, the main initial products of the oxidation and precipitation
281 of ferrous iron bearing solutions, which can be formed at surficial temperatures (Schwertmann and
282 Fitzpatrick 1992). After Out-Ca (#6; pH = 6.2), Fe was removed from solution.

283 3.2.1.2. Aluminium speciation

284 According to Macías et al. (2012), aluminium could be trapped as hydroxysulfates in the white precipitates
285 shown in Fig. 2a', which could also contain gypsum. The most abundant Al aqueous species in the AMD-
286 Input #1 were associated with sulphate compounds [AlSO_4^+ , $\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$], which were replaced by
287 hydroxylated species along the DAS-Ca column [AlOH^{2+} , $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_2^+$]. Mid2-Ca (#4; pH = 5.8).
288 Precipitation of Al species (Fig. 5b) such as alunite [$\text{KAl}_3(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_6$], basaluminite
289 [$\text{Al}_4(\text{SO}_4)(\text{OH})_{10} \cdot 5(\text{H}_2\text{O})$], jurbanite [$\text{Al}(\text{SO}_4)(\text{OH}) \cdot 5(\text{H}_2\text{O})$] and Al-hydroxides [$\text{Al}(\text{OH})_{3(\text{am})}$, gibbsite
290 $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, boehmite $\text{AlO}(\text{OH})$ and diaspore $\text{AlO}(\text{OH})$] would be significant as pH increases (Nordstrom and
291 Alpers, 1999). Our results point that alunite (SI = 13) and basaluminite (SI = 14) could have exercised the
292 main control of Al solubility (Fig. 5b). Sánchez-España et al. (2005) suggested basaluminite as the most
293 probably Al phase precipitating at a range of pH between 3.3 and 5.7, although its solubility is largely

294 influenced by adsorption-coprecipitation with Fe-rich sulphates (Sánchez-España et al., 2016). After Mid3-
295 Ca (#5; pH = 6.4), Al was removed from solution.

296 3.2.1.3. Trace element partition

297 Trace element partition from solution to secondary Fe-Al solid phases is associated to adsorption and/or
298 coprecipitation processes. Mineralogical studies of ochreous-precipitates in acid environments suggest that
299 jarosite-rich (together with schwertmannite-rich) precipitates contain the highest concentrations of As and
300 Cr among all the poorly crystalline oxyhydroxysulphates (Sánchez-España et al., 2016), as well as other
301 toxic elements such as Cu, Pb and Zn (Hammarstrom et al., 2005). On the other hand, ferrihydrite-rich
302 precipitates seem to be characterized by high concentrations of Pb and relatively high content of Zn and Ni
303 (Marrescotti et al., 2012). Indeed, As and Pb showed a drastic decrease in concentration associated with Fe
304 and possible precipitation of H- and K-jarosite (see graphical abstract, ocre-Fe shadow section). The
305 behaviour of Cr under acid conditions should be controlled by jarosite (Sánchez-España et al., 2016) and
306 schwertmannite (Sánchez-España and Reyes, 2019). However, the homogeneous depletion of Cr below
307 Mid2-Ca (Fig. 3c, E; pH≈6) suggested that ferrihydrite could be involved, or directly Cr(III) precipitation
308 as Cr(OH)₃ could have occurred.

309 No data for saturated Cu species were obtained before Mid2-Ca #4. Until that point, main species in solution
310 were Cu²⁺ and CuSO₄. Conditions at Mid2-Ca could have allowed the precipitation of Cu-sulphates (Fig.
311 5c) as antlerite (Cu₃(SO₄)(OH)₄, SI = 0.55) and brochantite (Cu₄(SO₄)(OH)₆, SI = 1.42), stable phases at
312 near-neutral condition (Delgado et al., 2009; Shum and Lavkullich, 1998). After the DAS-Ca column,
313 soluble species CuCO₃, CuHCO₃⁺ and CuOH⁺ appeared. Carbonate and bicarbonate aqueous species
314 rapidly disappeared after entering the DAS-Mg column, probably due to precipitation of carbonate phases
315 (Fig. 5c) such as malachite [Cu₃(CO₃)₂(OH)₂] and, in less extent, azurite (SI_{Out-final} 1.62 and 0.61,
316 respectively) or associated with Cu-sulphates as brochantite (Carbone et al., 2013). Noticeable changes in
317 colour in the column solid and liquid due to poorly crystalline blue-green precipitate phases (Fig. 2a') could
318 support this interpretation.

319 Evolution of aqueous Zn species in the system is very close to that of copper. Zinc cation, ZnSO₄ and
320 Zn(SO₄)₂⁻ were the present species before treatment. At the contact with DAS-Ca, sulphated species were
321 diminished in favour of bicarbonate ones (ZnHCO₃⁺). At the Out-Final, ZnCO₃ represented 25% of aqueous
322 compounds. Only smithsonite (SI = 0.29) and monohydrate zinc carbonate (ZnCO₃:1H₂O, SI = 0.56)
323 reached oversaturation, showing that the treatment was not enough to totally remove Zn from solution.

324 Papassiopi et al. (2014) also reported similar results in AMD affected waters. According to Zachara et al.
325 (1991), in calcareous environments at relatively high concentrations of divalent metals (DAS-Mg column),
326 their aqueous concentration (including Cd, Mn and Zn) is governed by precipitation of discrete metal–
327 carbonate phases. The hydrochemical model pointed to oversaturation of rhodochrosite [MnCO₃] at Out-
328 Mg (#11) and Out-Final (#12) (SI of 0.75 and 1.51, respectively). However, according to Jensen et al.
329 (2002), precipitation kinetics of rhodochrosite is slow. The alkaline conditions of the final treatment
330 allowed the saturation of carbonated phases such as huntite [CaMg₃(CO₃)₄], calcite or dolomite, which
331 could be involved on coprecipitation-sorption processes, affecting solubility of Zn, Mn and other trace
332 elements. The higher efficiency of Cu and, in less extent of Zn retention, seemed to be determined by
333 Cu/Zn-rich phases like antlerite and brochantite at Mid1-Ca (see Graphical abstract, White-Al and Green-
334 Cu shadow). . In AMDs derived from Zn-rich source materials the processes would involve the formation
335 of Zn-sulphates (bianchite, serpierite, goslarite, etc., not registered in Phreeqc databases), substitution of
336 Zn/Cu in typical phases like antlerite and brochantite, or substitution of Zn/Fe and Zn/Al in different hydro-
337 sulphates as melanterite, copiapite, dietrichite or halotrichite group (Jambor et al., 2000). The high
338 percentages of Zn²⁺ and ZnSO₄ registered in solution supports these statements.

339 The behaviour of toxic elements could be also controlled by phosphate phases, especially after the DAS-
340 Ca column. In fact, the most effective PO₄⁻³ depletion occurred at pH < 3, when probably strengite
341 [Fe(PO₄)·2(H₂O)] precipitated. This effect could limit the presence of MnHPO₄ in the DAS-Mg at the first
342 centimetres, where PO₄⁻³ was available (Fig. 5d). On the other hand, a significant uptake of Cu, Zn, Co, Ni,
343 Cd and Mn can be noted between Supra-Mg (#7) and Mid2-Mg (#10), as other studies report (Macias et
344 al., 2012; Rötting et al., 2006).

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346 **3.2.2. Rare earth fractionation pattern**

347 Poorly crystalline iron oxyhydroxysulphates can act as a preferential sink of MREE by co-precipitation-
348 adsorption processes (Bau, 1999). The weathering of the disseminate orebody in Zaruma-Portovelo is the
349 main source of aqueous REE (and pollutants) to the catchment basin. The first control point, AMD-Input,
350 a typical hydrogeochemical AMD environment (acidic pH, high salinity, high sulphate concentration)
351 revealed high ΣREE concentrations (average of 754 µg/L). In addition, (La/Gd)_{NASC} and (La/Yb)_{NASC}
352 presented values lower than 1 (Table 3), suggesting MREE and Heavy REE (HREE) enrichment compared
353 to Light REE (LREE). ΣREE, sulphates and phosphates decreased to 68.6 µg/L, 1912 mg/L and 0.85 mg/L,
354 respectively after DAS-Ca (especially at Out-Ca). A strong correlation (R²=0.99) exists between

355 sulphate/iron and REE concentrations, indicative of the precipitation of efflorescent salts and Fe-
356 oxyhydroxysulphates coats able to remove lanthanides from solution (Bigham et al., 1996; Pérez-López et
357 al., 2010).
358 On the other hand, previous studies have demonstrated that the distribution of REE in AMD often shows
359 NASC-normalized convex patterns with an evident MREE enrichment with respect to LREE and HREE
360 (Verplanck et al., 1999; Ferreira da Silva et al., 2009). The “Input treatment” (AMD-input and Sup-Ca)
361 showed a noticeable MREE enrichment, typical of convex REE NASC-normalized patterns (Fig. 6) and
362 consistent with the positive values of E_{MREE} ($+0.35 \pm 0.007$ with $R^2 = 0.99$). $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ values remained
363 >0 along the middle section of the treatment (Out-Ca and Sup-Mg). Nevertheless, the presence of
364 lanthanides decreased dramatically (average $E_{MREE} = 0.06 \pm 0.27$; $R^2 = 0.92$) suggesting REE fractionation
365 processes along the treatment. Finally, at the Out-Mg or “output treatment”, REE concentrations fell off
366 the detection limit and the distribution pattern depicted a sawn plot, which clearly illustrates the absence of
367 MREE enrichment. This REE behaviour illustrates a selective fractionation process affecting REE during
368 the treatment, which can be clarified in the subsequence section.

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370 **3.2.3. REE speciation in experimental treatment**

371 Sulphates were the main ligands present in AMD (Table 3) and presumably controlled the REE speciation
372 model in accordance with numerous studies in other sulphide mining districts worldwide (Olías et al., 2005;
373 Zhao et al., 2007). REE in AMD solutions are mostly complexed forming $LnSO_4^+$ and free trivalent-REE
374 (Ln^{3+} , referring to any lanthanide) (Gammons et al., 2005). Regarding the aqueous-speciation, REE-
375 sulphate complexes, mainly monosulphate-complexes ($LnSO_4^+$), were the main aqueous form at the “input
376 treatment” (63% mean) followed by $Ln(SO_4)_2^-$ species (31%) and free ionic species (Ln^{3+} , 6.3%) (Fig. 7a).
377 These results assimilated to those of Leybourne and Johannesson (2008) and Fernández-Caliani et al.
378 (2009) in sulphide areas, and that of Pérez-López et al. (2010) at the Iberian Pyrite Belt, which suggested
379 that where sulphate concentrations were high (> 2000 mg/L), $Ln(SO_4)_2^-$ in solution played an important
380 role in REE speciation processes. An important reduction in soluble $Ln(SO_4)_2^-$ species occurred at the
381 highest decrease of SO_4^{2-} concentration which confirmed the link between SO_4^{2-} and REE concentrations
382 (Ferreira da Silva et al., 2009). On the contrary, $LnSO_4^+$ and Ln^{3+} species remained practically unaltered in
383 solution. In addition, REE geochemistry in AMD solutions is strongly linked to pH, and to neutralization
384 processes. The partition among solid phases occurs at pH values between 5 and 6 (Wood et al., 2006).

385 Indeed, REE were removed from AMD at pH 6.9, whereas, at lower pHs (< 4.5), REE stayed in solution,
386 showing a conservative behaviour. In general, partition processes could have started before the Out-Ca
387 sampling point (pH 6.2) (Fig. 7b).

388 In the DAS-Ca column, formation of Fe-ochre precipitates and Al-oxyhydroxysulphates depleted REE from
389 AMD, probably due to limestone dissolution and sorption onto Fe-Al precipitates (Verplanck et al., 2004).
390 However, the analysis conducted in *Cheaq-Next* revealed that when Fe (11.38 mg/L) and Al (1.06 mg/L)
391 were practically consumed, REE partition continued. Therefore, carbonate and phosphate species present
392 at *Out-Ca* (pH > 6, pE = 8.6 and gross-alkalinity next to 300 mg/L) could have probably enabled REE
393 partition as $\text{Ln}(\text{CO}_3)^+$, $\text{Ln}(\text{CO}_3)_2^-$ and $\text{LnH}(\text{CO}_3)_2^+$ (mean values of 11.6, 0.94 and 0.92%, respectively).
394 After that, in *Supra-Mg*, carbonated species increased 36.0, 12.6 and 1.64%, respectively, at a time that
395 sulphate species halved in solution. However, not only CO_3^{2-} and SO_4^{2-} participated in REE partition
396 process. Saturation index computed by *Cheaq-Next* for LnPO_4 was 3.9 at *Out-Ca* and 4.5 at *Supra-Mg*,
397 showing super-saturated conditions and precipitation of phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) species. PO_4^{3-} could have also
398 contributed to partition of Ce and Gd after *Out-Ca*. (Fig. 7a). Gammons et al. (2005) suggested super-
399 saturation of LnPO_4 and hydrous phases (Ln were mainly La, Ce, Nd and Gd), controlling the natural REE
400 attenuation in mixing acid-neutral waters.

401 In summary, a complete depletion of REE can be observed along the water progress throughout the PTS.
402 This trend is characterised by low retention (3.6%) of total REE in the first steps (*Supra-Ca*) associated to
403 Fe-oxyhydroxysulphates, an effectively REE partition (91%) associated to Al-rich solid phases in *DAS-Ca*
404 column, and REE depletion to <0.1 indicating the total removal of REE in the first section of the *DAS-Mg*
405 column associated to minor lanthanide phases. While some authors (Verplanck et al., 2004; Prudêncio et
406 al., 2015) attribute REE retention mainly to ochre precipitates in abandoned mines and passive treatment
407 systems, this investigation shows a more complex partition progress in acidic waters. Moreover, these
408 results complete other REE behaviour studies during water mixing processes (Gammons et al., 2005; Wood
409 et al., 2006), and preliminary investigations from a pilot scale passive treatment system (Ayora et al., 2016).

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414 3.4 Efficiency of treatment and legislation issues

1 415 Results of Table 1 have been compared with reference values for irrigation waters (FAO, 1985) and
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3 416 consumption (WHO, 2011), and with the maximum values of discharges of elements in natural water bodies
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5 417 adopted by the Government Ecuadorian (MAE, 2003).

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7 418 pH and acidity values after treatment were in the range proposed by the FAO and WHO (6.5 to 8.5).
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9 419 Although sulphate retention is high compared to recent studies (Rötting, Thomas et al., 2008; Macias et al.,
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11 420 2012), final SO_4^{2-} concentration (1850 mg/L) was still above the established limit of 1000 mg/L (MAE,
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13 421 2003). According to Cabrera et al. (2006), these systems are ineffective in eliminating large amounts of
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15 422 sulphate due to the high metallic load, because these metals are toxic for the establishment of bacterial
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17 423 communities that reduce sulphate.

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20 424 A metal removal around 100% was achieved for Fe, Al and Cu, and higher than 70% for the rest of elements
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22 425 except Cr (~50%) and SO_4^{2-} (~25%) (Fig. 8). Therefore, the combined DAS system is suitable to treat AMD
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24 426 of Ecuadorian mining areas, and probably any other in the world. Comparing the element concentrations
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26 427 of the Out-Final water with the guideline values for toxic elements in irrigation and drinking waters (Table
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28 428 1), chemical quality of the treated waters accomplished these recommendations for most elements. Some
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30 429 values were slightly superior to the guidelines, but only Mn and Zn concentrations clearly surpassed those
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32 430 limits. Taking into account that drinking waters should be subjected to a drinking treatment, an additional
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34 431 analysis after those treatments should define their adjustment to human consumption. However, the results
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36 432 have also been compared with the maximum values of element discharges in natural waterbeds, adopted by
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38 433 the Ecuadorian Government (MAE, 2003).

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41 434 As previously discussed, the DAS-Mg columns reflected a passivation stage by the end of the experiment,
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43 435 which specially affected to Zn retention. By 16/09/2014, Zn retention was around 95%, and on 20/02/2015,
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45 436 it decreased to 43% (Table 1). The rest of divalent metals did not undergo major changes, overcoming
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47 437 overall effective retentions of 80%. In this case, the final concentrations of Mn and Zn surpass these
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49 438 referenced limits. The discharge of these waters to rivers, as well as their use for agriculture, should be
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51 439 preceded by additional treatments for Mn and Zn reduction.

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54 440 The high metal removal can be related to the sulphate reducing conditions achieved in the DAS-Mg, which
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56 441 is confirmed by the negative values of net-acidity and p.e. values of the Out-Final flow (Table 2: acidity -
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58 442 285 mg/L as CaCO_3eq ; p.e. 7.23). Passive treatments are usually not effective removing large quantities of
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60 443 sulphate from AMD due to the high-metallic load because metals could be toxic for sulphate reducing

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444 microbial (SRM) communities (Utgikar et al., 2003; Cabrera et al., 2006). In addition, there might not have
445 been strict anaerobic conditions for SRM to thrive. The development of fermenters is also crucial to provide
446 organic acids as carbon sources to be utilized by SRM. Therefore, the addition of a final step to promote
447 the enrichment of SRM should be tested, without dismiss other system as adsorption or ion exchange
448 processes.

449 Additionally, the control of hydraulic conductivity reflected the capability of the system of working under
450 low and high flows (Fig. 9), proving the existence of an adequate permeability during long treatment
451 periods. Moreover, the effectiveness of the treatment seemed not to be controlled by the climatic conditions,
452 even if an increase of precipitation was registered (October 2014 15th and February 20th 2015).

453 Taken into account the good response of STP, the recovery of some base metals and REE have been
454 calculated and reported in the Table 4. The high concentration obtained for some metals make it possible
455 to consider the potential recovery of metals in acid system treatment, such as Al, Cu, Fe or Zn. The potential
456 possibility of recover metals in treatment of mine waters has previously been reported by other studies
457 (Smith et al., 2013), which proposed metal recovery by solubilization of the sludge from AMD treatment
458 under soft acid conditions. This possibility can be brought to this experience, since metals are finally
459 retained in poorly crystalline oxy-hydroxides and/or oxy-hydroxysulfates. Moreover, the solid-waste could
460 contain remarkable concentrations (0.11 gr during 8 month of treatment) of high-tech metals such as REE,
461 which could be also considered as valuable by-products (Macias et al., 2017). In fact, the potential metal
462 recovery of Torata flow would be 24 kg/yr. Moreover, other valuable industrial metals such as Mn (tons/yr)
463 could increase the potential value of Zaruma-Portovelo mine waste.

464

465 **5. Conclusions.**

466 The passive treatment system responded positively during the 8 months of experimentation in the
467 laboratory, removing quantities of metals even higher than previously achieved by other systems. This fact
468 justifies the implementation of the DAS at field-pilot plant for real flows.

469 The visual observation of precipitated layers shown the important role of Fe (III) on metal retention along
470 the first centimetres of the DAS-Ca column, in form of low-crystalline oxyhydroxydes mainly jarosite,
471 schwertmannite and lepidocrocite (geochemical model support this statement). Aluminium is trapped
472 deeper as hydroxysulfate, as well as gypsum. In fact, white precipitates observed also confirm this idea.

473 Data of the second state of treatment (DAS-Mg) suggested that carbonates (calcite-dolomite, and in lesser
474 extent azurite-malachite) were involved on coprecipitation-sorption processes, affecting solubility of Zn,
475 Mn and other divalent metals. Moreover, the abundance of Zn would condition the existence of Zn-
476 sulphates. High percentages of Zn^{2+} and $ZnSO_4$ registered in solution supported these statements. In
477 general, the experiment confirmed that DAS-Mg column contributes to a total retention of divalent metals.
478 In addition, the behaviour of toxic elements could be also controlled by minority phosphate and carbonate
479 phases.

480 Finally, since the concentration of sulphates after treatment contravenes existing local legislation, an
481 improvement of the system that promotes sulphate remotion is necessary.

482 Concerning REE fractionation processes, the study confirms the traditional trend of these elements
483 associated to sorption onto Fe-Al rich precipitates. However, REE partition continued even when Fe and
484 Al were consumed, so the role of carbonates and phosphates was also depicted in this REE partition. Finally,
485 a reutilization of the solid wastes obtained from the columns can be a new-fangled source of metals and
486 REE to the current market and could significate an excellent revalorisation of the solid-wastes. For this
487 reason, a new approach, by mean of mineralogical characterization and selective extraction, it is actually
488 being done to test the possibility of these wastes as a secondary source of metals and REE with economic
489 interest.

490

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710 TABLES

711 **Table 1** Hydrochemical mean results of the main steps of treatment after the first and the last month of
 712 experience, including statistics of AMD sources (Buza and Torata) and concentration restrictions for toxic
 713 elements proposed by FAO (1985), WHO (2011) and Ecuadorian National Government (MAE, 2003)

714 **Table 2** Phreeqc modelling input data from sampling 20/02/2015 of Torata AMD

715 **Table 3** CHEAQS-Next modelling input data from sampling 20/02/2015 of the treatment

716 **Table 4** Metal retention values from laboratory experimental columns (gr) and their potential annual
 717 removal values (tons/yr) assuming a field pilot-plant to decontaminate the average outflow of 1 L/s from
 718 Torata mine shaft

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720 FIGURES

721 **Fig. 1** Map of Zaruma-Portovelo mining district (ZPMD) showing punctual waste-water discharges
 722 associated to metal-processing plants, environmental liabilities and ranges of polluted zones with toxic
 723 elements (Modified from Ayala and López, 2014)

724 **Fig. 2** Passive multi-step treatment system based in the DAS concept. **a)** Photography shown the treatment
 725 during July 2014 (starting operation); **a')** Photography showing both Ca- and Mg-DAS column during
 726 monitoring before 8 month of treatment (February 2015, end of the operation experiment); **b)** Schematic
 727 design of system showing most important setup parameters

728 **Fig. 3** Distribution of water master variables (mg/L) along the stages of the passive treatment **a)** Fe, Al, net
 729 acidity and pH; **b)** Ca, Mg and sulphates; **c)** Cu, Zn, Mn, Cd, As, Pb, Co, Cr and Ni after the first month of
 730 treatment (Buza AMD-Input; Fe=Fe*10), **d, e, f)** after the last month (Torata AMD-Input; Fe=Fe/5)

731 **Fig. 4** Evolution of parameters in the preferential sampling-points of the treatment (from 15/07/2014 to
 732 20/02/2015). The change of water source is represented by the orange (AMD_{BUZA}) or blue (AMD_{TORATA})
 733 background of the plots. **a)** Net acidity (mg/L CaCO₃ eq; **b)** Al; **c)** Fe; **d)** Zn

734 **Fig. 5** Results of Phreeqc-software modelling obtained along several control point (Sampling Ports shown
 735 in Figure 2) of passive treatment system. Aqueous species and solid-phases saturation indexes for: **a)** Al-
 736 rich and; **b)** Fe-rich phases; **c)** Cu- and Zn-rich phases; **d)** saturation indexes of some minor phases reported
 737 by model. Other refers minor phases whose values were always below 1%

738 **Fig. 6** NASC-normalized REE patterns for solution of the passive treatment system. Input treatment: AMD-
 739 Input + Supra-Ca; Middle treatment: Out-Ca + Supra-Mg; Output treatment: Out-Mg + Treated output.
 740 The shadowed area refers to the variability range and dash line to the mean value

741 **Fig. 7** Results of aqueous speciation from Torata AMD last sampling. **(A)** Average ratios of REE for Ln³⁺
 742 aqueous species (where Ln = Lanthanides except Ce and Gd plotted separately). **(B)** Comparison between
 743 variation of the relative abundance of La³⁺ in AMD of the Iberian Pyrite Belt (Ayora et al., 2016, Figure 2)
 744 and Ln³⁺ species obtained in this study from AMD of ZPMD, showing the evolution based on pH and the
 745 different section of treatment control. Thermodynamic data from MEDUSA database (Puig-Domenech,
 746 2010)

747 **Fig. 8** Boxplot showing the degree of efficiency of total treatment time as metal removal percentage
 748 between input-AMD (laboratory) and output container

749 **Fig. 9** Trend of hydraulic conductivity (K) during the treatment showing the high flow period (4 weeks)
750 and inter-annual (2014-2015) mean climate range (source INAMHI, Nacional Institute of Meteorology and
751 Hydrology) to test the efficiency of the columns with different residence times and metal concentration
752 input

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Figure 1

Table 1

		Code d.l.	pH	E.C.	Alk	Acidity	Ag 0,013	Al 0,02	As 0,05	Ca 0,005	Cd 0,008	Co 0,005	Cr 0,018	Cu 0,043	Fe 0,005	Mg 0,005	Mn 0,019	Ni 0,017	Pb 0,044	Zn 0,17	SO ₄ ²⁻ 2
Input source	Buza/First sampling (15/07/2014)	AMD-Input	2,7	4,7	<20	4361	0,02	531	0,07	416	7,03	2,12	0,13	335	121	202	66,8	0,24	0,19	698	4707
		Supra-Ca	4,1	4,1	<20	2200	0,03	194	0,05	999	6,41	2,21	0,06	203	4,98	218	63,2	0,22	0,12	654	3757
		Out-Ca	5,9	3,9	183	973	0,05	1,26	0,05	1128	6,36	2,39	0,05	61,2	0,42	212	68,8	0,28	0,08	668	3212
		Supra-Mg	6,7	4,1	190	283	0,02	0,16	<d.l.	788	2,66	0,99	0,03	16,9	0,13	699	35,8	0,02	0,03	296	3176
		Out-Mg	8,8	4,4	76	-70	<d.l.	0,08	<d.l.	389	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,20	0,17	1114	1,71	0,01	0,02	1,05	3254
		Out-Final	8,1	4,6			0,05	0,09	<d.l.	246	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,19	0,14	1089	1,73	0,01	0,02	0,91	3633
	Torata/First sampling (16/09/2014)	AMD-Input	2,5	3,0	20	426	0,01	83,5	2,06	95,1	0,62	1,00	0,01	29,8	474	109	21,3	0,92	0,19	71,7	2934
		Supra-Ca	2,5	2,9	20	429	0,1185	95,6	2,33	122	0,84	1,02	0,01	37,1	456	123	22,7	0,92	0,20	91,7	2108
		Out-Ca	5,8	2,2	190	34,5	<d.l.	0,97	0,10	729	1,26	1,06	0,01	56,5	8,59	120	24,0	0,97	0,08	109	2001
		Supra-Mg	6,0	1,9			<d.l.	0,26	<d.l.	695	1,55	1,09	0,01	33,3	0,60	138	25,4	0,95	0,04	132	1904
		Out-Mg	9,3	3,1			<d.l.	0,01	<d.l.	206	0,04	0,03	0,01	0,73	0,16	431	0,83	0,02	0,02	2,85	1730
		Out-Final	8,5	3,3	190	-116	<d.l.	0,01	0,04	220	0,01	0,08	0,01	0,12	0,14	413	1,86	0,03	0,01	3,88	1733
	Torata/Last sampling (20/02/2015)	AMD-Input	2,4	2,6	20	1307	0,21	57,6	12,4	129	0,38	1,23	0,04	13,6	488	134	25,7	1,39	0,17	43,9	3075
		Supra-Ca	2,3	1,9	20	1089	0,12	53,6	4,64	101	0,28	1,10	0,04	10,7	391	107	21,3	1,21	0,34	34,2	2500
		Out-Ca	6,2	1,5	263	-173	0,11	0,01	<d.l.	824	0,30	1,10	0,02	8,56	0,01	117	21,7	1,16	0,01	31,9	2150
		Supra-Mg	6,7	2,1			0,04	0,01	<d.l.	835	0,23	0,91	0,02	6,69	0,01	133	21,4	0,99	0,01	26,5	1950
		Out-Mg	7,1	1,7	255	-188	0,07	0,01	<d.l.	602	0,04	0,76	0,02	1,07	0,01	288	15,9	0,48	0,01	24,5	1825
		Out-Final	8,0	1,6	343	-285	0,09	0,01	<d.l.	494	0,06	0,39	0,02	0,57	0,01	334	9,83	0,28	0,01	25,1	1850
Legal limits	FAO	6.5-8.4				n.d.	5	0,1	n.d.	0,01	0,05	0,1	0,2	5	n.d.	0,2	0,2	5	2	n.d.	
	WHO	6.5-8.5		n.d.		n.d.	0,9	<d.l.	n.d.	0,003	n.d.	0,05	2	2,0	n.d.	0,4	0,07	0,01	3	n.d.	
	TULSMA					0,1	5	0,1	n.d.	0,02	0,5	0,5	1	10	n.d.	2,0	2	0,2	5	1000	

E.C.: Electrical conductivity (mS/cm); Alk: Total alkalinity as mg/L of CaCO₃; n.d. no data reported; d.l. detection limit; Data expressed in mg·L⁻¹

Table 2-Revised

Sampling Port	AMD-Input 1	Supra-Ca 2	Mid1-Ca 3	Mid2-Ca 4	Mid3-Ca 5	Out-Ca 6	Supra-Mg 7	Mid1-Mg 8	Out-Mg 11	Out-Final 12
pH	2,4	2,3	2,4	5,8	6,4	6,3	6,6	7,3	7,0	8,0
Temp (°C)	21,5	21,5	21,7	21,7	21,7	21,2	21,5	21,7	21,6	21,9
Eh _H (mV)	821	794	772	344	460	507	445	406	465	409
pe	13,9	13,4	13,1	5,82	7,78	8,57	7,52	6,86	7,85	6,91
Alkalinity*	20	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	366	n.d.	n.d.	341	409
Ca	118	125	153	804	1027	873	857	177	602	714
Mg	119	125	140	142	177	162	242	547	394	366
K	3,12	3,17	3,75	3,5	3,65	4,00	3,99	4,57	4,25	4,56
Fe	230	257	259	6,82	<d.l.	0,02	<d.l.	0,02	0,02	0,01
Mn	26,3	27,9	31,1	30,0	31,7	27,5	28,0	6,47	19,0	9,64
Cr	0,06	0,05	0,07	0,03	0,02	0,03	0,03	0,01	0,02	0,02
Co	1,54	1,54	1,61	1,67	1,18	1,40	1,24	0,11	0,66	0,61
S(6)**	4535	4579	3177	2454	1959	1842	1567	1900	2088	1512
P***	7,3	7,9	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0,90	0,90	n.d.	0,90	1,00
Ag	0,2	0,25	0,22	0,07	0,12	0,07	0,18	0,05	0,10	0,20
Al	61,2	64,3	72,4	58,6	0,08	0,08	0,09	0,06	0,08	0,09
As	7,05	7,50	4,18	0,03	0,06	0,03	0,04	0,01	0,02	0,03
Cd	0,40	0,41	0,39	0,33	0,15	0,19	0,21	0,11	0,07	<d.l.
Cu	16,0	16,1	17,8	33,1	0,54	1,32	0,56	0,28	0,22	0,24
Ni	1,72	1,71	1,81	1,87	1,25	1,45	1,33	0,09	0,56	0,68
Pb	0,74	0,22	0,19	0,13	<d.l.	0,01	<d.l.	<d.l.	<d.l.	<d.l.
Zn	46,8	48,8	55,0	52,0	13,4	12,5	13,7	7,02	3,90	3,05

Concentrations are expressed in mg·L⁻¹ (* Alkalinity as HCO₃⁻ ** S(6) as SO₄⁻² *** P as PO₄⁻³) / n.d. not determined; <d.l. below detection limit Calculations based on the Oxidation-reduction potential: Eh_H(mV)=Ehpl(mV) + 223.8 - 1.02*t(°C); pe=16.9*(Eh_H/1000)

Solution	AMD-Input	Supra-Ca	Out-Ca	Supra-Mg	Out-Mg	Out-Final	unit	type of input value
Elements								
La	5,30E-02	5,13E-02	6,45E-03	4,04E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Ce	1,32E-01	1,27E-01	9,77E-03	5,88E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Pr	2,19E-02	2,12E-02	2,41E-03	7,59E-04	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Nd	1,28E-01	1,23E-01	1,16E-02	3,73E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Sm	4,52E-02	4,35E-02	2,28E-03	7,88E-04	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Eu	1,58E-02	1,53E-02	9,15E-04	< d.l.	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Gd	8,80E-02	8,46E-02	9,26E-03	2,92E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Tb	1,60E-02	1,54E-02	1,72E-03	6,94E-04	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Dy	1,04E-01	1,00E-01	7,12E-03	4,08E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Ho	2,30E-02	2,21E-02	3,65E-03	1,09E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Er	6,46E-02	6,22E-02	5,89E-03	3,23E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Tm	8,42E-03	8,12E-03	1,25E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Yb	4,80E-02	4,64E-02	5,42E-03	< d.l.	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Lu	7,03E-03	6,79E-03	8,00E-04	< d.l.	< d.l.	< d.l.	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Ligands								
PO₄³⁻	7,90E+00	9,25E+00	8,50E-01	1,00E+00	1,05E+00	9,50E-01	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
SO₄²⁻	4,53E+03	4,47E+03	1,91E+03	1,75E+03	1,96E+03	1,89E+03	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
CO₃²⁻	1,20E+01	1,20E+01	1,80E+02	1,74E+02	1,68E+02	2,01E+02	mg·L ⁻¹	total concentration
Parameters								
Alkalinity	20	20	300	290	280	335	mg·L ⁻¹ *	total concentration
pH	2,4	2,3	6,2	6,7	7,1	8,0		-
pe	13,71	13,19	8,57	8,32	8,25	7,23		-

* Alkalinity as mg·L⁻¹ for HCO₃⁻ / < d.l. below detection limit.

Calculations based on the Oxidation-reduction potential: $E_{H_i}(mV) = E_{p_i}(mV) + 223.8 - 1.02 \cdot t(^{\circ}C)$; $pe = 16.9 \cdot (E_{H_i}/1000)$

Table 4

Total Recovery Treatment	240 days					
	Flow: 1 month at 0,66 L/Day and 7 month 1,44 L/day					
Basic metal Concentration (mg/L)	Al	Cu	Fe	Mn	Zn	ΣREE
	64,7	16,8	796	57,6	19,4	0,754
gr (8 month)	20,2	6,49	18,8	8,18	13,3	0,11

Total Simulation	1 year					
	Flow: 1 L/s (Torata mine shaft mean annual value)					
mg/day	55832587	28916585	10455996	60239287	1280413	65146
Total recovery (Kg/yr)	20379	10555	3816	21987	467	24
Tons/yr	20	11	3,8	22	0,5	0,024